

3D REM-based Positioning Procedure for UAV-Assisted Het-Nets

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Abstract—The recent advances in wireless communications toward upcoming services and infrastructure have spurred the development of unmanned aerial vehicle (UAV) assisted terrestrial networks. They offer the prospect of significant capacity improvement through the aerial base station (ABS), particularly when it leverages three-dimensional (3D) radio environment maps (REMs) that provide spectrum occupancy characterization. The heterogeneous network (Het-Net) with an ABS scenario consists of a stationary ground base station (GBS), an ABS and mobile users. Motivated by the 3D REMs' potential and their limited application in the field, this work introduces a heuristic procedure for ABS positioning that integrates the collection of received signal strength (RSS) measurements to update the REM, Kriging-based 3D REM reconstruction, and user association with the ABS. The experiments determine the 3D REM sampling rate and, consequently, the amount of necessary measurements, based on the highest achievable system capacity. In addition, this novel solution is compared to reference methods for UAV positioning through extensive simulations, showing an increase of up to 15% compared to alternative algorithms, reaching a maximum capacity of 128 Mbps.

Index Terms—Het-Net, Kriging, UAV-assisted networks, user association, UAV positioning, 3D radio environment maps, resource allocation.

I. INTRODUCTION

The continually increasing node density in modern and upcoming communication systems, and the diverse use cases that they are applied in, have led to multiple challenges as well as opportunities for the industry's development beyond the Fifth Generation (5G) [1]. These scenarios include enhanced mobile broadband on the ground and in the air through heterogeneous deployments of user-centric ultra-dense networks and unmanned aerial vehicle (UAV) assisted

radio access, industrial Internet of Things (IoT), integrated terrestrial and space networks, emergency communications, as well as service provision in remote regions. UAVs have been established as a major technological enabler for the implementation of these services as it provides increased coverage and reliability, flexible adaptation, universal availability, improved network self-organization and scalability [2]. These features make the UAV-based aerial base station (ABS) an important node within upcoming heterogeneous network (Het-Net) architecture that combines multiple applications, communication technologies, and types of terminals, which are powered by agile algorithms. From a wireless communications perspective, the delivery of these features requires the adaptive allocation of the network resources, i.e. energy (power) and available spectrum, which establishes the three-dimensional (3D) characterization of the limited spectrum as a current problem [3]. 3D Radio Environment Maps (REMs) have been established as an essential tool for spectrum utilization characterization and adaptive resource allocation. These REMs describe the variation in the received signal strength (RSS) in 3D space. A crucial question in the integration of UAVs in Het-Nets is the aerial communication nodes' positioning (or placement) in a variety of use cases such as relaying of terrestrial or satellite user data, broadcasting, and UAV-to-UAV communications [4].

A. Related Works and Research Motivation

Despite of the large number of studies on the design of ABS-assisted networks [5], 3D REMs have not been extensively applied for the implementation of their communication procedures. Hereby, some prominent works with REM-based operations for UAVs, coupled with standard network scenarios are reviewed, so as to emphasize the novelty of this paper. They may be categorized according to the system models that they use as:

- Cellular-connected UAVs - UAVs that are being served by the ground base stations (GBS). Such works employ

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reinforcement learning (LR) for ABS positioning [6], user association for interference management between ABS and GBS [7], and measurement collection for Kriging-based REM reconstruction [4].

- ABS for terrestrial UEs - the users are directly associated to the UAV without considering stationary APs. Such works focus on ABS for data harvesting of stationary IoT devices [8], ABS transmission power control [9], and REM reconstruction on the basis of measurements from the UEs [10].
- ABS-assisted terrestrial network - the APs' service reliability is supported and extended by the UAV, which is associated to UEs that experience coverage degradation. This use case constitutes the system model for the proposed solution and defines its focus. The authors of [11] find appropriate areas by assigning weights according to the distance between the users and the ABS. Thus, they reduce the computational complexity while optimizing the number of served users. In [12], a modified K -means algorithm is employed to determine the ABS position so that the users' requirements are satisfied while not interfering with other ABSs. Building upon these methods, the authors of [13] explore a variant of this system model with the UAV's trajectory being designed as a Markov decision process to determine the locations over which the ABS will hover for a certain period. Its purpose is to provide wireless charging to stationary IoT UEs, and at the same time, collect data from the GBS and the UEs. Further, [14] investigates the ABS' positioning and its association to the UEs, such that it maximizes the minimum capacity for all users. Furthermore, the Gaussian Process (GP) model [15] has also been employed for optimization of coverage and reduction of the UAV's energy consumption.

Considering the application of the UAV as an aerial base station (ABS), as per the categorization made in [2], this work introduces a method for coverage extension of ground-based infrastructure, and the capacity improvement of freely-moving UEs that operate in the "Terrestrial Het-Net space" (as shown in Fig. 1) below the "UAV operational space" that denotes the region of the ABS's operation. The placement of the ABS is enabled by 3D REMs that describe the radio environment of the UEs. In this paper, a terrestrial network is incorporated into the Het-Net 6G architecture through the ABS (illustrated in Fig. 1) to achieve ubiquitous 3D coverage and seamless user mobility. Thus, the aerial node which acts as both an RF sensor and an ABS that provides service to the UEs. The operating procedures of the system are illustrated in Fig. 1 and summarized in the following tasks:

- 1) Measurement phase - the UAV collects RSS measurements of the channels utilized by the UEs attached to the GBS, to reconstruct the 3D REMs.
 - a) The Kriging method, preliminary calibrated from our previous work [16], is used for 3D REM reconstruction.

- b) The 3D REM is used by the ABS to determine the serving position z_a at which the ABS will be positioned while serving its UEs to improve their downlink (DL) capacity.

- a) The REM is also used to estimate the set of N_z positions to be used in the next measurement cycle.

- b) After the ABS position is established, it is associated to the UEs with low capacity.

- 4) Serving phase - taking advantage of the improved link provided by the ABS, the UEs retain their QoS as they transition from the stationary GBS into the ABS without manual reconfiguration.

This work proposes a procedure for the completion of these tasks, and establishes its performance gains. The main contributions are summarized as follows:

- A heuristic procedure for establishing the position of an ABS that provides extended coverage to low-capacity UEs of a terrestrial network. The positioning is based on 3D REMs reconstructed via the Kriging method from the UEs' uplink (UL) RSS measurements. The complete 3D REM is comprised of the sum of the individual maps of all UEs and is used to determine both the ABS serving position and the locations at which the UAV will perform future measurements to update the map.
- The 3D REM sampling rate, respectively, the amount of necessary measurements, is determined empirically, based on the highest achievable system capacity. The proposed solution's efficiency is verified through a comparison to reference ABS positioning methods achieving up to 128 Mbps or 15% improvement compared to alternative baseline methods.

The rest of this paper is organized in the following manner. Section II describes the system model and formulates the problem under investigation. Then, the solution is detailed in Section III, while the results are illustrated and discussed in Section IV. Finally, the conclusions and aspects for future work are given in Section V.

II. SYSTEM MODEL AND PROBLEM FORMULATION

A. System Model

The system model is comprised of an individual segment of a ground network that includes a stationary GBS and N_{UE} UEs, which are initially associated with it. The set \mathbb{U} , with $|\mathbb{U}| = N_{UE}$ is comprised of all UEs (smartphones and robots/IoT devices) in the system. They move in 3D within the terrestrial network volume, which is denoted as \mathbb{B} , defined by the lengths of S_x^b , S_y^b , and S_z^b in the x , y , and z axes, respectively. Within this volume there are also $N_{\mathbb{B}}$ UE movement locations. The UE movements are modeled via the random walk algorithm. First, the UEs are placed according to the Matern distribution [17] with density λ_{UE} , which determines N_{UE} , and a minimum distance $d_{min,UE}$ between every two UEs. At each consecutive iteration, each UE moves from one location, defined by specific coordinates in x , y , and z

Fig. 1. 3D REM based positioning procedures for the ABS.

axes, to another with different coordinates. These movements, unrestrained within \mathbb{B} , are performed with a random speed $\theta \in [0; \theta_{max}]$, where θ_{max} is the user's maximal speed, and direction according to a randomly selected angle $\phi \in [0; 2\pi]$. The UAV flies only within the UAV operational volume, denoted as \mathbb{A} , specified with lengths of S_x^a , S_y^a , and S_z^a in the x , y , and z axes, respectively. It performs measurements and based on them, reconstructs the 3D REM $\tilde{\Psi}$. The GBS serves the UEs by default, while those with DL RSS from the GBS below a threshold τ , are associated with the UAV and will be served by it. It is assumed that the backhaul between the ABS and the GBS is present and outside of the scope of this investigation.

The ABS and the GBS operate on two non-overlapping sets (denoted as \mathcal{U} and \mathcal{V}) out of all N_{ch} available bands, with $\mathcal{U} = \{u_0, u_1, \dots, u_{N_{\mathcal{U}}-1}\}$ and $\mathcal{V} = \{v_0, v_1, \dots, v_{N_{\mathcal{V}}-1}\}$, respectively, where $N_{\mathcal{V}} = \delta_{\mathcal{V}} * N_{ch}$ and $\delta_{\mathcal{V}}$ is the portion of channels that are to be allocated to the GBS users, and $N_{\mathcal{U}} + N_{\mathcal{V}} = N_{ch}$. The DL RSS $P_{UE_i}^{DL}$ of the i -th UE is described as follows:

$$P_{UE_i}^{DL} = h_t P_{t,T}^{\mathcal{W}_i} + P_0, \quad (1)$$

where \mathcal{W}_i is the set of channels allocated to this UE with $|\mathcal{W}_i| \geq 1$, $P_{t,T}^{\mathcal{W}_i}$ is the transmission power of the serving node $t = \{GBS; ABS\}$ that the UE is associated to (GBS or ABS), and h_t is the channel coefficient that describes the path loss (PL) coefficient, and P_0 is the noise power. The GBS-UE link is modeled as the traditional distance-dependent path-loss model [18], while the ABS-UE link uses the modified two ray ground-to-air PL model described in [19]. The signal-to-noise ratio (SNR) is represented as:

$$\sigma_{UE_i}^{\mathcal{W}_i} = \frac{P_{UE_i}^{DL}}{P_0 * NF_{UE}}, \quad (2)$$

where NF_{UE} is the UE's noise figure. Then, the system capacity \mathcal{T} is defined as of the sum of each user's individual

capacity \mathcal{T}_{UE_i} :

$$\mathcal{T} = \sum_{i=1}^{N_{UE}} \mathcal{T}_{UE_i} = \sum_{i=1}^{N_{UE}} |\mathcal{W}_i| \mathcal{B} \log_2(1 + \sigma_{UE_i}^{\mathcal{W}_i}), \quad (3)$$

where \mathcal{B} is the channel bandwidth.

The UAV flies within \mathbb{A} where it performs regular measurements for the duration of N_m iterations for the measurement phase. After having determined its position and the UEs it associates with, the ABS provides service for them in the span of N_s serving iterations for the serving phase. These UEs form the set \mathbb{U}_a , with $N_{\mathbb{U}_a} = |\mathbb{U}_a|$, while the rest of the users comprise the set \mathbb{U}_u , with $N_{\mathbb{U}_u} = |\mathbb{U}_u|$, and $N_{\mathbb{U}_a} + N_{\mathbb{U}_u} = N_{UE}$. It should be noted that the measurement and serving phases follow after each other, and spectrum measurements are not performed simultaneously with the service provision to the UEs, as it is assumed that the ABS is equipped with only one transceiver for both spectrum sensing and communication with the UEs. The 3D UAV operational volume is divided into $M_{\mathbb{A}} = N_x * N_y * N_z$ points, which denote the UAV positions on the x , y , and z axis, correspondingly for N_x , N_y , N_z . The RSS measurement $P_{UE_i}^{UL}$ at a location l is denoted as:

$$P_{UE_i}^{UL} = h_a P_{T,UE_i}^{\mathcal{U}} + P_0, \quad (4)$$

which describes received signal over the set of frequency channels \mathcal{U} , at which the ABS performs the sensing, $N_{\mathcal{U}}$ is the number of channels in \mathcal{U} , while l denotes the coordinates (i, j, k) . $P_{T,UE_i}^{\mathcal{U}}$ is the UE's uplink transmission power. For the sake of generality, the set \mathcal{U} of uplink UE channels is the same as the set \mathcal{W} comprised of the DL channels.

B. Kriging-based 3D REM Reconstruction

By combining the RSS levels $P_{UE_i}^{UL}$ for all $M_{\mathbb{A}}$ locations, the tensor $\Psi_i \in \mathbb{R}^{N_x \times N_y \times N_z}$ is formed. The locations of the recorded measurements form the subset $\mathcal{Z} = \{z_0, z_1, \dots, z_{N_{\mathcal{Z}}-1}\} \subset \mathbb{A}$ with $N_{\mathcal{Z}}$ being the number of locations within \mathcal{Z} , and $N_{\mathcal{Z}} = \rho M_{\mathbb{A}}$, where ρ is the 3D

REM's sampling ratio, which denotes the fraction of all points within \mathbb{A} at which measurement samples were collected. They are then used to obtain the reconstructed 3D REM $\tilde{\Psi}_i$ through the Kriging method. It is described in detail in [16], while the specific parameters, i.e. the number of samples for Kriging interpolation $\eta_K = 5$ and the smoothness parameter $\nu_K = 1.55$ are calibrated using the process and data described in [20]. The REMs for all UEs are summed to obtain the overall map $\tilde{\Psi} = \sum_{i=1}^{N_{UE}} \tilde{\Psi}_i$.

C. Problem Formulation

This Section describes the optimization problem for determining the ABS positioning and UE association to the UAV so as to enhance the overall network capacity \mathcal{T} . It is illustrated analytically in (5), defining the objective to maximize \mathcal{T} and describing the two operations of ABS positioning and user association, denoted as 2.2 and 3.2 in Fig. 1. The ABS has to find the location $z_a \in \mathbb{A}$ at which \mathcal{F}^U , comprised of the sum of $P_{UE_i}^{UL}$ for all UEs, is minimum. The rationale for choosing this position is that it corresponds to a section of the volume at which the ABS-UE channels are least utilized, so that they can be exploited for the corresponding links. Thus, the task includes finding the position at which the sum \mathcal{F}^U of the DL RSS $P_{UE_i}^{DL}$ of all these links is maximized. The ABS is to attach to at least one UE, i.e. form the set \mathbb{U}_a , while the rest will continue to be served by the GBS (the set \mathbb{U}_u).

$$\begin{aligned} \max \mathcal{T} &= \sum_{i=1}^{N_{UE}} \mathcal{T}_{UE_i} \\ \text{s. t. } z_a \in \mathbb{A}, z_a &: \{ \min \mathcal{F}^U; \max \mathcal{F}^D \} \\ \mathcal{F}^U &= \left(\sum_{i=1}^{N_{UE}} P_{UE_i}^{UL} \right), \mathcal{F}^D = \left(\sum_{i=1}^{N_{UE}} P_{UE_i}^{DL} \right) \\ N_{\mathbb{U}_a} &\geq 1, N_{\mathbb{U}_u} = N_{UE} - N_{\mathbb{U}_a} \end{aligned} \quad (5)$$

III. PROPOSED SOLUTION

Before the solution may be obtained, the UAV measurement positions should be determined, as they are the basis upon which the 3D REMs are reconstructed. For this reason, the criterion \mathcal{C}_0 in (6) is used. This criterion chooses $N_{\mathcal{Z}}$ locations (assumed to be equal in number to N_m) with the lowest RSS values of the last reconstructed REM $\tilde{\Psi}$. The rationale for selecting these comes from the literature on spectrum sensing for cognitive radio [21]. It shows that the user's signal is less likely to be detected when it is weak, therefore, it is the areas of low RSS that are the most important for the UAV sensor to perform measurements at. The number $N_{\mathcal{Z}}$ is determined for $\rho \leq 30\%$, as small $N_{\mathcal{Z}}$

implicitly leads to lower energy consumption for the UAV, and increases its opportunity to serve the UEs.

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{C}_0 : \mathcal{X} &= \{x \in \mathbb{A} \mid \mathcal{F}^U(x) \leq \mathcal{F}_{(N_{\mathcal{Z}})}^U\}, |\mathcal{X}| = N_{\mathcal{Z}} \\ \forall x, (x \in \mathbb{A} &\Leftrightarrow x \in \tilde{\Psi}), \\ N_{\mathcal{Z}} &= \rho * M_{\mathbb{A}} = N_m, \rho \leq 0.3 \end{aligned} \quad (6)$$

The solution to (5) is found via heuristically solving the two criteria in (7) and (8) that correspond to tasks 2.2 and 3.2 in Fig. 1, respectively. It should be noted that the solutions for the ABS positioning and user associations are decoupled from the REM reconstruction and the choice of UAV measurement positions but the latter supply the preliminary spectrum information used for solving (7) and (8). The 3D REM $\tilde{\Psi}$ is obtained through the Kriging method [16]. Then, the algorithm obtains the position z_a at which the UAV will hover as it serves its associated UEs, considering that their number will be at least one, i.e. $N_{\mathbb{U}_a} \geq 1$. The ABS positioning is determined through the criterion \mathcal{C}_1 that chooses serving position z_a as the index l at which the highest \mathcal{F}^D is obtained. It is selected from the set \mathcal{Y} comprised of the $N_{\mathcal{Z}}$ smallest values of \mathcal{F}^U . Then, at this location, the ABS performs the user association by fulfilling \mathcal{C}_2 in the following two steps. First, the ABS determines a subset u_n of UEs that have DL \mathcal{T} (from the GBS), which is lower than the threshold τ , i.e. all UEs with poor coverage. The channel allocation is not considered in the problem, as the channels that comprise the sets \mathcal{V} and \mathcal{U} for the users associated to the GBS and the ABS, respectively, are allocated at random.

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{C}_1 : z_a &= z_l \mid l = \arg \max [\mathcal{F}^D (y \in \mathcal{Y})] \\ \mathcal{Y} &= \{x \in \mathcal{X} \mid \mathcal{F}^U(x) \leq \mathcal{F}_{(N_{\mathcal{Z}})}^U\} \end{aligned} \quad (7)$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{C}_2 : \mathbb{U}_a &= \{u_l\}, \\ \{u_n\}, n &= \{i \in \{1, \dots, N_{UE}\} : \mathcal{T}_i < \tau\}, \\ |u_n| &\geq 1, |\mathbb{U}_u| \leq N_{UE} - |\mathbb{U}_a|. \end{aligned} \quad (8)$$

The criteria \mathcal{C}_0 , \mathcal{C}_1 and \mathcal{C}_2 are implemented by the operations described in Algorithm 1. First we define the sets of channels \mathcal{V} and \mathcal{U} , system parameters $N_{UE}, N_I, N_{ch}, N_m, P_{UE,T}, P_{GBS,T}, P_{ABS,T}, \delta_{\mathcal{V}}$, the scenario lengths for each of the axes S_x, S_y , and S_z , as well as the propriety coefficient $C_P \in \mathbb{Z}$, which is defined as the number of serving cycles for which the 3D REM will be relevant before it is updated. A serving cycle is comprised of the N_s iterations during which the UEs are served by either only the GBS or by both the GBS and the ABS. L is the update index that drives the simulation's states based on the C_P . The algorithm operation follows the following processes. For every measurements phase (i.e. $L = 0$), the UAV collects measurements, while the GBS serves all UEs. In the first instance, i.e. when the ABS measurements index I_m is 0, the set of measurement locations \mathcal{Z} is comprised of random points within \mathbb{A} . For consecutive instances of the measurement phase ($I_m > 0$), \mathcal{Z} is determined from the last reconstructed 3D REM using the criterion \mathcal{C}_0 . Afterward, the ABS uses the obtained

measurements to reconstruct $\tilde{\Psi}$ using the Kriging method, and determines its serving position z_a and its associated UEs via the criteria \mathcal{C}_1 and \mathcal{C}_2 , respectively. The ABS positioning and UE associations are retained for $C_P * N_s$ iterations. Then, the sets of channels \mathcal{U} and \mathcal{V} are allocated among the users associated to the UAV and the GBS, respectively, for the duration of N_s iterations. The network capacity \mathcal{T} is calculated and the UEs movements are modified. The overall system bandwidth is $BW = N_{ch} * \mathcal{B}$. The user associations remain the same for $L * N_m$ iterations.

Algorithm 1 3D REM-based ABS positioning and UE associations

Input: $\mathcal{V}, \mathcal{U}, N_{UE}, N_I, N_{ch}, N_m, P_{UE,T}, P_{GBS,T}, P_{ABS,T}, \delta_{\mathcal{V}}, S_x, S_y, S_z, S_x^b, S_y^b, S_z^b, S_x^a, S_y^a, S_z^a, C_P, \lambda_{UE}$

Output: \mathcal{T}

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1: for  $p = 1$  to  $N_I$  iterations do
2:   if  $L == 0$  then
3:     Allocate all  $N_{ch}$  channels to the GBS for all UEs
4:     if  $I_m == 0$  then
5:       Choose random locations that comprise  $\mathcal{Z}$ 
6:     else
7:       Determine  $\mathcal{Z}$  based on  $\mathcal{C}_0$ 
8:       Set  $I_m = I_m + 1$ 
9:     end if
10:    The ABS measures  $P_{UE_i}^{UL} \big|_{i=1}^{N_{UE}}$  at each  $z_l \in \mathcal{Z}$ 
11:    if  $\text{mod}(p, N_m) == N_m - 1$  then
12:      Reconstruct the 3D REM  $\tilde{\Psi}_i$  on the basis of the
13:      previous  $N_m$  measurements
14:      Obtain  $\tilde{\Psi} = \sum_{i=1}^{N_{UE}} \tilde{\Psi}_i$ 
15:      Determine the ABS serving location  $z_a$  using (7)
16:      Find  $\mathcal{T}_i, i \in \{1, \dots, N_{UE}\}$ 
17:      Determine  $\{u_n\}, \mathbb{U}_a$  and  $\mathbb{U}_u$  using (8)
18:      Set  $L = 1$ 
19:    end if
20:    if  $L \in [1; C_P + 1]$  then
21:      Allocate the sets of channels  $\mathcal{U}$  and  $\mathcal{V}$ 
22:    end if
23:    if  $L > C_P$  then
24:      Set  $L = 0$ 
25:    end if
26:    Calculate  $\mathcal{T} = \sum_{i=1}^{N_{UE}} \mathcal{T}_i$ 
27:    The UEs move with speed of  $\theta$  at an angle of  $\phi$ 
28:  end for

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IV. SIMULATION RESULTS

This Section outlines the parameters (Table I) under which the simulations are performed, and also details the findings and their significance. The simulation is run on an Intel Core i9-13900KF Processor at 3.00 GHz, 64 GB of random access memory (RAM), solid state drive (SSD), and an NVIDIA GeForce RTX 4070 (12 GB) graphical processing unit (GPU), Python 3.12 and Tensorflow 2.17. The simulation volume boundaries are denoted as $[-(S_x/2); (S_x/2)]$ for the x -axis,

$[-(S_y/2); (S_y/2)]$ for the y -axis, and $[-(S_z/2); (S_z/2)]$ for the z -axis. The GBS is positioned at coordinates $[0, 0, 10]$, i.e. in the middle of the simulation region at height of 10 m following the Third Generation Partnership Project (3GPP) recommendations in the report TR 38.901 [22] for GBSs in the Urban Micro (UMi) scenario. The UEs are distributed through the Matern method with density of λ_{UE} . The UAV operational volume and the terrestrial network volume are limited within their respective axes lengths as defined in Table I.

TABLE I
SIMULATION PARAMETERS

Parameter	Value
N_I	10^5
N_m	100
S_x, S_y, S_z	150, 150, 20 m
S_x^b, S_y^b, S_z^b	150, 150, 10 m
S_x^a, S_y^a, S_z^a	150, 150, 9 m
\mathcal{B}	180 kHz
N_{ch}	55
$\delta_{\mathcal{V}}$	0.5
F_c	2 GHz
$P_{GBS,T}, P_{UE,T}$	24, 23 dBm
σ_{NF}	9 dB
$d_{min,UE}$	0.3 m
δ_{max}	3 km/h
τ	5 Mbps
N_x, N_y, N_z	12, 12, 4
C_P	1

First of all, a set of simulations is performed to verify the interpolation accuracy of the Kriging method against established baseline Deep Learning (DL) methods such as U-Net and 2-layer Convolutional Neural Network (CNN) [23]. The latter two are preliminary trained with 5000 3D REMs generated using the simulated system model in Section II, and the saved weights are used in the simulation rather than Kriging. The results in Table II show that Kriging outperforms them in terms of normalized root mean square error (NRMSE) [16] as DL methods ordinarily require specific data analysis to improve their accuracy. This will be left to future work as this study focuses on the 3D REM-based positioning procedure described in Section III.

TABLE II
RESULTS FOR 3D REM NRMSE AS A FUNCTION OF ρ .

$\rho, \%$		5	10	20	31
NRMSE, dB	Kriging	8.12	5.98	1.82	-1.55
	UNet	32.16	30.17	26.57	21.59
	CAE	25.48	22.79	19.17	13.63

Several sets of simulations are performed to evaluate \mathcal{T} for the variable ρ and in comparison to the reference methods, with the parameters from Table I being constant. In this work N_s is taken to be equal to N_m .

Firstly, the simulation is performed for different values of $\rho = [5, 10, 20, 31] \%$, which correspond to $N_m = [30, 60, 120, 180]$, respectively. Fig. 2 shows the cumulative distribution function (CDF) of \mathcal{T} dependent on ρ . The best

performance is achieved for $N_m = 30$ with up to 8% higher capacity than the other options, and so it is set as a parameter for the comparison with alternative methods. In general, a lower N_m results in a higher capacity because with the measurement cycles being shorter, there are more opportunities for the ABS to serve the UEs. This is the reason why the second highest \mathcal{T} is obtained when $\rho = 10\%$. There is, however, only a small difference in the results, which becomes much more prominent for higher ρ . Considering the 3D REM reconstruction accuracy (Table II), naturally the NRMSE declines with the increase of ρ but that does not significantly influence the capacity.

Fig. 2. CDFs of \mathcal{T} for different values of ρ

To emphasize the performance gains of the proposed ABS positioning method, it is compared to alternative reference scenarios for the ABS positioning but the UE association is still performed through the procedures (lines 15-16) described in Algorithm 1 (Fig. 3). Five reference methods are considered - K -means [12], and maximum sum (Max Sum) rate [24], weighted area [11], maximization of the minimum capacity for all users based on the 3D REM (termed 3D REM MaxMin) [14] and the GP optimization [15]. The results are obtained by executing them for each set of N_{UE} UE locations for the specific iterations at which there is an update of the ABS position when $N_m = 30$. Then the acquired ABS positions are applied in the simulation. The results for the weighted area method represent the best benchmark with the proposed method as the latter yields up to 15% greater \mathcal{T} . The other two methods exhibit CDFs very close to each other with about 5% lower \mathcal{T} than the weighted area. The benefit from utilizing the proposed procedure based on 3D REM, is shown in the substantial improvement of the \mathcal{T} , as it reaches over 85 Mbps in over 50% of the simulation period. This emphasizes the 3D REM's robustness to the wireless channel fluctuations caused by the dynamics of user movements, without modeling them explicitly. Both the proposed solution and the reference the MaxMin algorithm apply the same 3D REMs reconstructed through Kriging. Determining the posi-

tion from the $N_{\mathcal{Z}}$ positions with lowest \mathcal{F}_U improves on the alternative only slightly (at about 2%), and does not require the measurement of \mathcal{F}_U for all locations in \mathbb{A} , thus being less computationally complex and more feasible for real-world implementations. To further contextualize the performance

Fig. 3. CDF of the \mathcal{T} for the proposed ABS positioning method against reference ones.

of the proposed method, it is compared to more advanced ABS positioning algorithm, namely the GP optimization. The latter provides the optimal placement but iterates over all $M_{\mathbb{A}}$ possible ABS locations to find the solution to satisfy all N_{UE} users. Therefore, this method has significant computational complexity but allows for determining an upper benchmark based on expressing the ABS positioning task as a GP. The 3D REM based algorithm achieves capacity that is only up to 5% lower than the the benchmark and follows its distribution closely, thus exhibiting the proposed method's capability.

V. CONCLUSIONS

This paper presents a novel procedure for ABS positioning, based on 3D REMs, reconstructed via the Kriging method, which describe the dynamic radio environment, and includes the user association for UAV-assisted terrestrial networks. The simulation setup is detailed, and the proposed solution is compared to reference methods for UAV positioning, achieving noteworthy improvement in capacity. This work has practical significance as it shows that Kriging-based 3D REMs with small number of measurements can provide significant capacity gains. The results highlight the following prominent aspects that provide hints into future research:

- The 3D REM update period may be an important factor in the proposed procedure representing a topic for future work. A more developed and realistic application of this ABS positioning and user association will consider an optimization of the 3D REM update and UAV serving periods so as to adapt the radio access to the variable spectrum availability and decrease the overhead exchange.

- The proposed solution can be expanded for an application to a system model that incorporates both incumbent and cognitive radio enabled nodes, the latter being served by the ABS. This will include an agile learning of the 3D REM, ABS positioning, and channel allocation that adapts to the interference constraints.

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